

Theoretical Problems of Studying the Psychological Time of an Individual

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Abstract: with the development of Physiology, the approach to temporal-spatial problems was radically changed the main interest was focused not on general issues of the origin of these forms of perception, but on many personal issues of physiological and psychological nature, putting the task of studying the laws of formation of the perception of time and space in ontogenesis.

Keywords: time, perception, development, ontogenesis, polymodality, kantianism, nativist, neoplasm.

Problems with the temporal Factor have different volumes, aspects, polymodalities and levels. They are discussed and studied in various fields of knowledge of philosophy and physics, biology and psychology. But, nevertheless, the main category of time remains one of the most relevant and at the same time long-lasting discussions.

Until the 19th century, it was believed that for people, time, like space, are innate forms of perception of reality (Kantianism, nativists). Problems of theoretical and practical study of time, including discoveries of global importance and many well-known names in the historical vertical of scientific research Plato and Aristotle, Augustine and Ibn Khaldun, Newton and Leibniz, Spinoza and Kant, Einstein and Heidegger, Ukhtomsky and Prigozhin, are solved by many unknowns and are often sufficiently conditional [90]. The degree of study of time in psychology is evidenced by the statements of a number of famous scientists. For Example, S. L. Rubinstein wrote: the problem of time has become one of the main problems in modern philosophy in recent years... and in psychology, this problem began to arouse great interest. But, unfortunately, it still did not develop enough" [144 P.254]. K. A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya " the problem of psychological time, despite the increasing number of his studies..., remains theoretically ambiguous. A single conceptual model has not been created..., there is no idea of degree about the relationship of psychological, personal and life time, the only picture of their diversity" [7 p.66-67]. A. G. Asmolov clarified the state of affairs in this area as follows:" in psychology, little is known about the nature of time in an offensive way " [28 P.97]. Psychological time is "unlucky", it is studied mainly in connection with spatial syntheses, so the data on the formation of temporal perception and perceptions is much simpler:" time travels little from level to level, but its evolution is less studied " (N. A. Bernstein, 1997 P.158); the development of genetically temporary structures later and often on the basis of spatial structures makes it difficult to study time [33 p. 31].

On the other hand, the problem of psychological time is not independent, it does not exist

clearly or clearly in research on dynamic, mental changes, personality changes in changing political and social conditions, arises every time trying to competently develop and create its concept.

The general state of development of the psychological time problem has determined that there are relatively independent directions and areas of study of this psychological phenomenon. First, we are talking about the perception and assessment of short time intervals, the study of elementary orientation over time (N. I. Chuprikova, 1979; L. M. Mitina, 1977; P. N. Belyaeva-instance, 1965; S. G. Gellerstein, 1958; V. P. Lisenkova, 1966; D. G. Elkin, 1962, 1969; N. D. Bagrova, 1980; P. Fress, 1961-1978). The second direction is the study of the concepts of the psychological period of the individual on the scale of individual biography (E. I. Golovaha, A. A. Kronik, 1984; N. S. Pryazhnikov, S. A. Ivanushkina, 1998). In addition, this area of study of time is based on the event approach to the study of the individual's Life Path (B. G. Ananiev, 1980; Sh. Buhler, 1980; N. A. Loginova, 1978; S. L. Rubinstein, 1996; K. A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, 1987), moreover, at the beginning of the analysis, the fact itself is not the intensity of events and Inter-event communication. With some adjustments to this direction, K. Levin (1980), N. Frank (1939), I. Newtten (1964), M. R. The works of Ginzburg (1994) include the study of the psychological or life prospects of the developed personality. K. A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya (1999), V. I. Kovaleva (1979), L. yu.Kublitskene (1989), O. V. Kuzmina (1993) works that study the forms of operation of subjective representations occupy an independent place in the study of the problem of psychological time.

Thus, in the psychological literature, the actual psychological time of an individual does not differ as an individual concept of psychological time, obtained as a result of all the dynamic processes of a person and on a b-roof or other scale (situation, biographical, historical). The latter, although reflecting the basic laws and characteristics of psychological time [144], however, can have subjective disorders that manifest themselves in planning errors and life prediction. In fact, psychological time is associated with any dynamic manifestation of personality, and in real life it is manifested in any manifestation of its installation activity. Installation as a unit of analysis of activities and activities in accordance with its nature already includes time parameters orientation, measure, "before", "after" [40 P.159], on the basis of which a sequence, rhythm of movements, "temporal pattern" is formed. The most promising object for explaining the elements of real psychological time is a primary, urgent-momentary relationship, a systemic neoplasm of activity and behavior that acts as a holistic regime of the individual at each specific moment (D. N. Uznadze, 1966; A. S. Prangishvili, 1968; Sh. A. Nadirashvili, 1974; Sh. N. Chkhartishvili, 1973). The involvement of values and personal meanings, including those of a temporary nature, in the assimilation-contrast space of the primary establishment, makes it possible to classify it as a categorical relationship of an individual (A. G. Shmelev, 1978, 1983). The fact that temporal parameters are determined not only in the initial conditions of the establishment of the need and the emergence of the state of its satisfaction, but also in the updated meaning and personal meanings, allows us to assume that the actual establishment of the necessary person involves a temporal aspect of activity.

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